

ASYMMETRIC SOLIDIFICATION OF THE LUNAR MAGMA OCEAN CAUSED BY TIDAL HEATING. Stephen Parman¹, Wenhao Zhao¹, Harriet Lau¹, and James Head¹, ¹Department of Earth, Environmental and Planetary Sciences, Brown University, Providence, RI 02912, USA, (stephen_parman@brown.edu).

Introduction: The Moon's structure and composition are asymmetric on a global scale. The lunar nearside contains the highest concentration of basaltic volcanism, and both the KREEP and high Fe-Ti components [1]. The farside crust appears to be substantially thicker than the nearside crust [2] and to be more primitive [3]. The results from the Chang'e 6 returned imply it is drier [4] and has a lower oxygen fugacity [5] than the nearside. GRAIL data indicate the elastic shear modulus is 2-3% lower in the nearside mantle than the farside mantle [6]. Lunar anorthositic meteorites show a broader range of compositions than the Apollo nearside samples, consistent with compositional dichotomy in the crust [7].

This fundamental dichotomy may have been produced during the hypothesized overturn of the lunar mantle after LMO solidification. Due to an inverted density gradient in the cumulates, the upper layers may have sunk to the core-mantle boundary, displacing deeper, higher Mg# material towards the surface [1]. If overturn was hemispheric in scale (degree 1), then the dense cumulates could end up largely on the nearside [8, 9]. However, it is not clear how the overturn hypothesis could produce the dichotomies in crustal Mg#, mantle fO_2 or H_2O content, or a thinner nearside crust.

An alternative hypothesis is that the LMO crystallized asymmetrically, starting on the farside and progressing to the nearside. This has been used to explain the Mg# difference in the crust [3] and implies a delay of a few percent in crystallization of the nearside [10]. The offset of the center of mass of the Moon has also been attributed to asymmetric crystallization, and a higher Mg# mantle on the farside [11]. Earthshine (heating of the lunar nearside by heat radiated from the Earth) has been invoked as a heat source to drive the asymmetric solidification [3].

Tidal Heating of the LMO: Tidal heating of the LMO during its crystallization provides an alternative heat source to drive asymmetric crystallization [12]. It not only induces an asymmetric thermal regime, but also provides an explanation for the >100 m.y. delay of LMO solidification (Figure 1). The model is zero-dimensional, and so nearside and farside differences are calculated simply by estimating how tidal heat would be distributed across the body when the Moon was much closer to Earth. Three dimensional models of tidal heating of the Moon suggest that 3D effects may enhance tidal heating on the nearside [13];

therefore, our estimates of the thermal asymmetry may be low.

Asymmetric solidification of a tidally heated LMO: During the first 100 m.y. of LMO crystallization, tidal heating equals heat loss, and the Moon is locked in a quasi-stable thermal state. Further cooling increases tidal heating (negative feedback) driving the temperature up, while heating above the stable point reduces tidal heating, causing cooling back to the stable point. During this time, the temperature differences between the nearside and farside are minimal (Fig. 1) and asymmetries in the early (first 40-60%) cumulates should be limited. The Moon escapes the stable state when it recedes far enough for cooling to outpace heating, and for further cooling to lower tidal heating. This should occur close to the critical melt fraction, which for the LMO should be around 40%. The positive feedback (more cooling decreases tidal heating) at this point causes rapid LMO solidification, within a few million years. The farside reaches this thermal 'cliff' sooner than the nearside, and in this time interval, the temperature difference between the nearside and farside spikes (Fig. 1). Typical model runs have 40-100 °C temperature differences, that last up to a few 10's of million years. Most of the asymmetry should be produced during the last 40% of crystallization, with little, if any, asymmetry in the early cumulates. Three dimensional models are needed to better

Fig. 1. Asymmetric tidal heating of the LMO. The temperature difference between the nearside and farside is minimal during the stable equilibrium stage (red and brown curves), and peaks in the time between the farside and nearside reaching the unstable point (gray band). The green curve (right axes scale) shows $T_{near} - T_{far}$, peaking at ~40 K near 4.35 Ga. Tidal heating rates and LMO temperatures for the lunar near and farside are computed by perturbing the tidal forcing distance by the radius of the Moon. From [12].

quantify these conclusions.

Compositional consequences: A key factor in determining the compositional asymmetries produced by tidal heating is the extent to which LMO magma convected and mixed between the warmer nearside and cooler farside. If there were no mixing, then there would be no compositional differences. The observed dichotomies suggest some mixing occurred. While physiochemical modeling of the asymmetrically solidifying LMO will be needed to quantify the expected asymmetries, the tidal heating model is consistent with a wide range of global dichotomies in:

1. *Anorthositic crust Mg#* - Remote sensing indicates mafic minerals in the farside crust have an average Mg# of 65 and a maximum around 75, while the nearside is ~10 Mg# units lower in both average and maximum [3]. Lunar meteorites suggest a similar difference [7]. Experimental LMO crystallization results show that this difference can be explained by a ~4% delay in crystallization of the nearside (assuming a well-mixed LMO)[10]. This translates to a 40-60 °C difference, in agreement with the tidal heating results (Figure 1).

2. *Crustal thickness* - The farside crust is estimated to be 15-20 km thicker than the nearside crust [2]. If warmer, less Al-depleted magma from the nearside is continually advected to the cooler farside, one result should be enhanced feldspar crystallization, and a thicker anorthositic crust on the farside.

Fig. 2. Asymmetric crystallization of the LMO driven by differential tidal heating. (A) Nearside-hot / farside-cold state at ~4.35 Ga, just as the farside has passed the unstable point and is cooling rapidly. (B) Post-4.35 Ga cumulates. Figure is not to scale.

3. *KREEP and high Fe-Ti component* - As the farside becomes fully solidified, the last dregs of the LMO should be swept to the nearside (Figure 2). This is consistent with the concentration of KREEP and high Fe-Ti (ilmenite) components on the nearside [1]. This process need not be perfectly efficient, and some pockets of KREEP could be stranded in thinned crustal regions on the farside, such as the SPA.

4. *Mantle H₂O and fO₂* - The samples returned by Chang'e 6 from the SPA are the only returned samples from the farside. If they are representative of the entire farside, they indicate that the farside mantle is lower in H₂O content [4] and in oxygen fugacity [5] than the nearside. As with KREEP, these are both consistent with incompatible elements (H, Fe³⁺) being concentrated in the last LMO dregs on the nearside.

5. *Mantle shear modulus* - GRAIL gravity data indicates that the elastic shear modulus of the nearside mantle is 2-3% lower than the farside [6]. This could be explained by higher FeO and H₂O in the nearside mantle, both of which lower shear modulus.

Tests: The asymmetric crystallization model predicts that the farside crust should be older than the nearside crust by up to a few 10s of millions of years. The precision needed to resolve such small time differences is difficult to achieve in single samples. Perhaps comparing detrital zircon populations from nearside and farside soils could provide a statistically robust test. The tidal heating model also predicts that most of the asymmetry should be restricted to the upper portions of the lunar interior. A lunar seismic network may be able to resolve such a distribution.

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